

The Equation for Exotic Charges - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the new 8T, and in particular the proof of the arbitrary variations term to vanish into fermions, it is possible to construct a longer Fermions chains, which has exotic charges. The longer the chain the less probable it will be detected in nature. Author provides the formula to for calculation of fermions charges, according to the length of the prime-fold chain.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The following is the original proof from the 8T thesis; notice that M is now the matrix tensor, g is the Ricci flow, which was the result of parametrizing the manifold to "s" variable.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

Equation reads, length to manifold, manifold to matrix, matrix to flow, flow to time. δg As amount of arbitrary variations, which by demands of stationarity we require to vanish. Discretizing and partitioning the term δg into a series of sub elements, we can derive the existence of fermions, i.e. showing that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

Given four elements distinct:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 > 0$$

$$\delta g_3 + \delta g_4 < 0$$

If

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 + \delta g_4 \neq 0$$

Then the overall series cannot vanish, by that logic we need even amounts of equal elements of pluses and minuses. The amount must be even and summed as zero, ensuring stationary Lorentz manifold. Suppose that we had three distinct elements, two pluses and minus:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 > 0$$

or

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 < 0$$

Demanding the series to vanish this will exclude this result, and so there could not be three distinct elements in the series, else the overall series will not vanish to zero. As a result of those sceneries, we require the series to have an even amount of variation elements, manifesting as two distinct elements in the series, which differ in sign. If we allow those sub elements in the series to vary as well, and by the above reasoning, there are only two elements in the series, they are varying in a discrete way, or forming a group. Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature

$$O: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination. $\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$ For example. Even though the sub elements in the series are varying, the overall series can vanish. Now, count all the ways of possible combinations of those elements. We are going to analyze by the integral signs. Since it is a group, there is a natural map, which change an element to itself. One built his analysis firstly on those natural maps. So:

$$(1(e)1(e)1)$$

$$2(e)2(e)2$$

$$(221)$$

$$(112)$$

$$(211)$$

$$(122)$$

$$(212)$$

$$(121)$$

Up to this point, reader is most likely familiar with the everything as these 8T fundamentals exactly as presented in the thesis. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. We have that in order the series to vanish and given the threefold combination, the charge of each particle must be a divisor of three. In order the series to vanish, given an even of elements, the charges we derived must summed as positive or negative, integer, plus or minus one. Combined with the condition of the threefold, we reached:

$$\delta g_1 = +\frac{2}{3}$$

$$\delta g_2 = -\frac{1}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 &= +1 \\ \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2 &= -1\end{aligned}$$

$$\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \Leftrightarrow \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2 \quad (1.3)$$

The pair in equation (1.3) will be permitted as it. Will pair exactly to zero, that is in agreement with the charges of elementary quarks and in the 8T arbitrary variations of curvature on the metric tensor. suppose that instead of three threefold combination, it took five to bring an element to itself, then the charge of each particle must be a five divisor. The new five-fold combination is given by (1.31)

$$\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \quad (1.31)$$

The charge of each arbitrary variation, if one is correct should be

$$\begin{aligned}\delta g_1 &= +\frac{\theta}{5} \\ \delta g_2 &= -\frac{Z}{5}\end{aligned}$$

In such way that the amount of each object in the set multiplied must summed as one. In the above example, the first element is appearing three times, and the second element appearing twice, so the overall combination, we can write:

$$\left(+\frac{\theta}{5}\right) * 3 + \left(-\frac{Z}{5}\right) * 2 = 1 \quad (1.32)$$

If one is correct, the first pair of exotic charges is

$$\begin{aligned}\delta g_1 &= +\frac{3}{5} \\ \delta g_2 &= -\frac{2}{5}\end{aligned}$$

Such that (1.32) would be satisfied.

$$+\frac{9}{5} - \frac{4}{5} = 1$$

if seven elements

$$\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \quad (1.31)$$

$$\delta g_1 = +\frac{4}{7}$$

$$\delta g_2 = -\frac{3}{7}$$

$$+\frac{16}{7} - \frac{9}{7} = 1$$

We can see that there is a pattern, first of all it takes a prime-fold quark chain to bring an element to itself. Starting from threefold combination with certain charges, the numerator is increasing by one each prime-fold chain, starting from the first threefold combination. So in order to find out the charges we need to know just how many elements are in the chain. For $n_1 = 1$ we have threefold combination of elements, so the charges are presented in the pair

$$\frac{n_1}{2n_1 + 1} \rightarrow \left(\frac{2n_1}{2n_1 + 1}\right), \left(\frac{-n_1}{2n_1 + 1}\right)$$

For $n_2 = 2$

$$\frac{n_2}{2n_2 + 1} \rightarrow \left(\frac{2n_1 + 1}{2n_2 + 1}\right), \left(\frac{-n_1 - 1}{2n_2 + 1}\right)$$

For $n_3 = 3$

$$\frac{n_3}{2n_3 + 1} \rightarrow \left(\frac{2n_1 + 2}{2n_3 + 1}\right), \left(\frac{-n_1 - 2}{2n_3 + 1}\right)$$

The formula to represent the charge of each prime fold chain pair is the following

$$\frac{n_k}{2n_k + 1} \rightarrow \frac{2n_1 + (k - 1)}{2n_k + 1}, \frac{-n_1 - k - 1}{2n_k + 1} \quad (2)$$

$$n_k = k;$$

$$k \in \mathbb{R}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)